

**DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS FOR
ACADEMIC RECOVERY AND ACCESSIBLE (ARAL) PROGRAM****Riwel D. Abria**

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ABSTRACT

Instructional materials are used consistently as teachers' aid to proceed with meaningful teaching and learning process, the development, construction and utilization of instructional materials are factors that caused teachers' difficulty in developing highly impactful instructional materials. This study described and examine the substantial elements in developing and validating instructional materials in teaching mathematics 6 under the ARAL program. The study used descriptive correlational research design and was participated by 150 randomly selected public elementary school teachers in the Philippines. Results of the study showed that Development of instructional materials in grade 6 mathematics under the ARAL program should be measured through elements or factors such as content quality, clarity of language and style. Meanwhile, the same could be comprehensively validated through using criteria such as creativity, relevance and practicality. On top of these criteria, in developing and validating instructional materials for grade 6 mathematics under ARAL program, content quality and creativity were foremost criteria to be considered. Hence, the quality of the content in instructional materials for grade 6 mathematics increases, the creativity of those materials also tends to increase.

Keywords:*development, validation, instructional materials, ARAL program, creativity, content quality***INTRODUCTION**

Philippine educational system advances the use of innovative and creative instructional materials that are necessary to establish quality instruction towards the attainment of quality education. Instructional materials are the primary materials and resources that teachers used in teaching and learning process to help learners obtain desired learning objectives and to facilitate effective, retentive and meaningful educative process. Instructional materials are commonly known as teachers' essential weaponry to delivery effective instruction. In the spheres of Philippine educational system, instructional materials are significantly developed based on the learners' readiness, interests and skills. These are used in order to establish highly engaging teaching and learning process. In the face of modern technology, development and utilization of instructional materials in the normal teaching and learning process have been reshaped. Traditionally, there are instructional materials which are used by learners as relevant support for their learning acquisition including textbooks, modules, visual aids and the like. On one hand, as advanced technology positively penetrates into the teaching and learning processes, teachers widely used technology-based instructional materials that abide with the current technological landscape and follow modern generation of learners' interests to modern devices.

While instructional materials are used consistently as teachers' aid to proceed with meaningful teaching and learning process, the development, construction and utilization of instructional materials are factors that caused teachers' difficulty in developing highly impactful instructional materials. In this line, instructional materials are also considered as resources which are used by both teachers and learners as they both engage in the teaching and learning processes. Also, the development and use of instructional materials are not abruptly made merely considering teachers' desire. Under the established principles in developing and using instructional materials inside the normal teaching set-up, quality and relevance are to be met in order to ensure that the developed instructional materials can help learners acquire significant concepts, principles and information surrounding the

topical content of subjects being taught. On one hand, the implementation of Academic Recovery and Accessible (ARAL) program becomes one of the recent educational policy in the Philippines which aims to help learners recover from the challenges they experienced in the teaching and learning process. The program also emphasizes the establishment of a free and effective national learning intervention program through intensive teaching and learning process. Consequently, it also encompasses that learners show mastery on essential learning competencies in reading, mathematics and science.

The development and use of relevant instructional materials under the ARAL program has been one of the foremost concerns of teachers who act as tutors and facilitators. The researchers observed that there are need to develop more inclusive, relevant, creative and innovative instructional materials which are to be used exclusively for ARAL program. Since the program aims to provide effective academic interventions to fill the learning loss experienced by learners, the researchers view that it is essential to examine the elements that are to be considered in the development of instructional materials for ARAL program. Significance of providing effective, creative and relevant instructional material for learners under the ARAL program lies heavily on its positive implication where these instructional materials can serve as academic support mechanisms to create meaningful learning process under the ARAL program. While the researchers observed that the Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines provides instructional materials, they also assumed that development of more contextualized, creative, relevant and interactive instructional materials can elevate the standards of teaching and learning process under the ARAL program. Validated instructional materials are recommend for use as supplemental instructional tool in teaching the core concepts across subjects in basic education (Araza & Magnaye, 2023). Adequacy, content and styles are the significant elements to consider to develop a very acceptable and impactful instructional materials (Suarez, 2025). General pedagogical practices strengthens instructional practices for higher order thinking emphasizing instructional material quality (Kim, 2025). Instructional materials' evaluation require a comprehensive presentation of content, language and layout. The developed materials should be appropriate with the level of skills and competence of learners (Irawan et al., 2018). In addition, evaluation criteria to create a highly relevant and effective instructional materials include content quality, format, presentation, organization and accuracy (Macalikod & Simpall, 2025).

Hence, this study described and examined substantial elements which teachers considered in the development and validation of instructional materials in teaching mathematics for grade 6 learners under the ARAL program. The study supported the Sustainable Development Goal 4 (Quality Education) as the study carefully and comprehensively examine the elements for the creation of effective instructional materials in grade 6 mathematics for ARAL program, teachers can obtain better understanding on the substantial areas which they need to emphasize to develop effective instructional materials. And, learners if are provided quality-based instructional materials, they can be able to fill their learning loss in mathematics thereby, enhance their basic and most essential learning competencies in mathematics.

OBJECTIVES

This study described and examine the substantial elements in developing and validating instructional materials in teaching mathematics 6 under the ARAL program. Specifically, this study answered the following:

1. How may the respondents describe the substantial elements in developing instructional materials for grade 6 mathematics under ARAL program in terms of content quality, clarity of language and style?
2. How may the respondents examine the criteria in validating instructional materials for grade 6 mathematics under ARAL program in terms of relevance, creativity and practicality?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the elements in the development of instructional materials and the criteria in validating the developed instructional materials for grade 6 mathematics under the ARAL program?

Hypothesis

H0₁: There is no significant relationship between the elements in the development of instructional materials and the criteria in validating the developed instructional materials for grade 6 mathematics under the ARAL program.

METHODOLOGY

This study used a descriptive correlational research design in order to describe and examine the substantial elements in developing and validating instructional materials in teaching mathematics 6 under the ARAL program. Thus, the study used a researcher-made survey-questionnaire. The developed survey-questionnaire was divided into two (2) parts. For part 1, it contained items relating to the elements in the development of instructional materials for grade 6 mathematics under ARAL program in terms of content quality, clarity of language and style while part 2 contained items relating to the criteria in validating instructional materials in terms of relevance, creativity and practicality. The study used a 4-Likert Scale such as: 4-Strongly Agree, 3-Agree, 2-Disagree and 1-Strongly Disagree. The study employed a simple random sampling technique which selected the participation of 150 public school elementary teachers in the Philippines. Thus, the developed survey-questionnaire was validated by three (3) experts in the field of education who were composed of concurrent professors in the graduate schools holding a Doctorate Degree in Educational Management and Supervision. Thereafter, the researcher conducted a pilot test which measured instrument's internal consistency. The same obtained a Cronbach Alpha result ($\alpha=.871$) which signified that the instrument was "Acceptable."

The researchers posted a call for participants through online teachers' community found on social media (Facebook). Thereafter, the researcher formally administered the developed survey-questionnaire. Then, the researcher formally sent a letter of invitation to the selected subject-respondents through their email. Once confirmed, the researchers sent a Google Form link which contained the developed survey-questionnaire. The researchers allocated 20-30 minutes to answer or fill the survey-questionnaire. When all responses have been completed, the researchers organized and stored the raw data collected through using MS Excel. Apparently, the researchers calculated the collected raw data through using relevant statistical tools. Thus, the researchers used mean, standard deviation and general weighted mean in order to describe the substantial elements in developing instructional materials for grade 6 mathematics under ARAL program in terms of content quality, clarity of language and style and examine the criteria in validating the developed instructional materials for grade 6 mathematics under ARAL program in terms of relevance, creativity and practicality. In addition, the researchers employed Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) in order to examine if there would be a significant relationship between the elements in the development of instructional materials and the criteria in validating the developed instructional materials for grade 6 mathematics under the ARAL program.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Instructional materials served as critical dimension to establish effective and meaningful instruction. The development of instructional materials requires substantial elements which can direct teachers who develop the materials, to ensure that they can positively implicate effective learning acquisition process. In addition, development of instructional materials put greater responsibilities for teachers in mathematics 6 as ARAL program is a newly implemented learning intervention program that fill learning loss and gaps experienced by learners. Further, development of instructional materials for ARAL program does not only end in its development phase, comprehensive validation also requires tedious and critical process to ascertain that the developed instructional materials are adequate and relative to learners' skills, readiness and interests.

1. **Elements in the Development of Instructional Materials for Grade 6 Mathematics under the ARAL Program.** The results showed that content quality obtained the highest mean (3.71) which was verbally described as "Strongly Agree." This signified that teachers acting as tutors pursuant to the policies mandated by ARAL program strongly agreed that content quality should be immensely considered and required in developing instructional materials for grade 6 mathematics. The findings further revealed that teachers strongly agreed that when content quality was highly considered in the development of instructional materials, all substantial contents including the objectives, input, activities and assessment tasks are aligned with the curriculum standards and other learning competencies in mathematics 6. In addition, teachers strongly agreed that quality of content underscored the accuracy of mathematical concepts whereas inputs and illustrations are to be presented properly. This also indicated that teachers strongly agreed on the presentation of in-depth and comprehensive breadth of content coverage focusing only on the essential learning competencies that learners ought to learn, without crafting other unnecessary inputs and activities that may potentially confuse the learners. On one hand, clarity of language obtained a mean score of ($m=3.24$) and style obtained a mean score of ($m=3.23$)

which were both verbally described as “Agree.” This implied that teachers also agreed to emphasize language and style as important element in developing instructional materials for grade 6 mathematics under ARAL program. Further, these also showed that teachers agreed that the use of age-appropriate language, clear and specific construction words could avoid learners’ confusion that could potentially hamper their effective learning process. Also, teachers agreed that style was also an important element to consider as it could encourage learners to learn consistently because the instructional materials could present visual appeal and layout as well as consistent presentation of mathematical concepts and activities. The results of the study supported the study of Kaufman (2020) which concluded that content quality served as the foremost standard in the development of highly effective instructional materials. In addition, similar study revealed that educators emphasized content quality as the determining factor of overall quality among instructional materials. Practically, the study implicated that teachers should always consider the quality of content because content of instructional material could possibly direct learners’ manner of acquiring mathematical concepts. When contents are substantially presented in the developed instructional materials, learning competencies are to be obtained consistently.

2. **Criteria in Validating the Instructional Materials for Grade 6 Mathematics under the ARAL Program.** The results showed that creativity obtained the highest mean score ($m=3.82$) which was verbally described as “Strongly Agree.” This signified that teachers strongly agreed on the importance of emphasizing creativity as a criterion in validating a developed instructional materials in mathematics 6 under the ARAL program. They expressed that instructional materials should present innovative activities rather than conventional learning tasks that could potentially discourage learners under the ARAL program to actively participate. In addition, teachers also strongly agreed that creativity as a criterion in validating instructional materials could cater the diverse knowledge, skills and competence of learners. The findings also signified that teachers’ creativity could be a primary asset to develop a highly impactful instructional materials under ARAL program provided that the program envisioned to fill learning gaps in mathematics. On the other hand, the relevance obtained a mean score of ($m=3.56$) and practicality gained a mean score of ($m=3.41$) which were both verbally described as “Strongly Agree.” The results indicated that teachers strongly agreed that emphasis on relevance could enable them to align their instructional materials to the learning standards and competencies required by the program. They were also in conformity that considering relevance could enable their learners to practically apply the concepts and tasks contained on instructional materials. On one hand, teachers also strongly agreed that practicality should also be required a significant criterion in validating instructional materials as it could provide consideration including the feasibility of the instructional materials whether the same could be implemented or not. Also, teachers strongly agreed that time considerations could also be contained as practical emphasis in validating instructional materials for grade 6 mathematics under ARAL program. The findings of the study supported the study of Ersoy et al. (2017) which concluded that creativity, practicality and sensibility were important indicators of a well-developed instructional materials. In addition, similar study showed that creativity was a significant domain to create highly impactful instructional materials. Practically, the study implicated that teachers should put strong emphasis on creativity, practicality and relevance to develop highly functional and well-designed instructional materials for grade 6 mathematics under the ARAL program.
3. **Relationship Between Between the Elements in the Development of Instructional Materials and the Criteria in Validating Instructional Materials for Grade 6 Mathematics under the ARAL Program.** The result showed that content elements in the development of instructional materials in terms of content quality obtained a moderate positive relationship to the criteria in validating instructional materials in terms of creativity ($r=.424$). This suggested that as the quality of the content in instructional materials for grade 6 mathematics increases, the creativity of those materials also tends to increase. The result suggested that when developing instructional materials, teachers should focus on enhancing the content quality which could vitally lead to the development of creativity in presenting and illustrating as well as utilizing such instructional materials. The findings supported the study of Rahmani et al. (2021) which concluded that teachers’ response to content quality and creativity

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dimensions in developing and validating instructional materials were highly significant to facilitate effective instruction. Practically, the study implicated that teachers as tutors in ARAL program should design, develop and validate their instructional materials without compromising its content and creative presentation.

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CONCLUSION

Development of instructional materials used in grade 6 mathematics under the ARAL program should be measured through elements or factors such as content quality, clarity of language and style. Meanwhile, the same could be comprehensively validated through using criteria such as creativity, relevance and practicality. On top of these criteria, in developing and validating instructional materials for grade 6 mathematics under ARAL program, content quality and creativity were foremost criteria to be considered. Hence, the quality of the content in instructional materials for grade 6 mathematics increases, the creativity of those materials also tends to increase.

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